

Determinants of learning outcomes with online teaching based on students' perception

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Abstract

Background: Research on the topic of determining success of online learning is on the rise. Defining the key success factors, i.e. determinants of online learning success, is extremely important, especially at present as all higher education institutions have been forced to try their hand at teaching with the help of technology.

Purpose: Thus a research examining factors of learning outcomes of online learning was conducted. Learning outcomes were modelled as dependent variable, while the set of independent model variables included: course design, student motivation, student self-regulation and dialogue (instructor-student, student-student).

Study design/methodology/approach: Five research hypotheses were tested by analysing data collected from the students of the University of Novi Sad. A structured questionnaire was employed to collect data on the attitudes of users (students) to online learning. Respondents expressed their views (perception) about statements and valued them on a 5 point Likert scale. The instrument was applied to a sample of 360 responses using PLS structural equation modelling.

Findings/conclusions: All five hypothesis were supported with the analysis, confirming the importance of research from the aspect of contribution to the literature dedicated to identifying the key success factors of online learning. Additional contribution refers to the research conducted in Serbia, i.e. at the University of Novi Sad.

Limitations/future research: A more detailed analysis of the model itself and the possibility of finding the interdependence of constructs that affect perceived learning outcomes and user satisfaction remains as an area for further research.

Keywords: online learning, success factors, learning outcomes, PLS modelling

Introduction

Organizing online learning at higher education institutions became the focus of research in a large number of scientific disciplines with the outbreak of the pandemic. Although the use of online platforms for collaboration and knowledge

exchange had existed before, with the onset of COVID-19 pandemic all higher education institutions were forced to adapt to the new situation (Mo, Hsieh, Lin, Jin & Su, 2021, Elneel et al, 2023). The teaching staff, technical support, as well as the students themselves in most cases had had no previous experience with online

master programs.

In terms of the faculty at which they studied, 213 (59.2%) of them were from the Faculty of Technical Sciences, while 147 (40.8%) were from the Faculty of Economics. Additionally, 35 (9.7%) of them were enrolled in vocational studies, while 325 (90.3%) were enrolled in academic studies.

The last demographic characteristic concerns the experience in attending online classes; 4 (1.1%) of the respondents said that they had no experience in attending online classes, 75 (20.89%) had insufficient, and 281 (78.1%) respondents said that they had enough experience in attending online classes.

2.2. Applied methods

All theoretical concepts used in this research have been taken from previous studies published in the scientific literature and they provide a theoretical, rational framework for this research.

The instrument was applied to a sample of 360 respondents using the structural equation model-based PLS methodology for two reasons. The first is that PLS is suitable for application in the early stages of theory development and testing. The more significant reason is that it is particularly suitable for analysing respondents' attitudes.

Latent variables, such as: attitudes, emotions, personality, motivation and the like, represent phenomena whose existence is concluded on the basis of observed behaviour. In this research, the respondents' attitudes were evaluated with a five-point Likert scale, and viewed as latent variables. Numerous authors have evaluated latent variables, i.e. examined complex interdependencies of latent constructs, with the aid of the statistical-econometric technique of structural equation modelling (SEM). SEM enables the modelling of the influence paths of latent constructs, i.e. variables that cannot be observed or directly measured.

Since latent constructs lack direct observations, they are operationalized, i.e. approximately measured using indicators that are called measurable, or manifest variables. For research conducted using questionnaires, each question in the questionnaire represents a measurable, manifest indicator. The parts of the structural equation model are: the structural model (in which the relations of latent constructs are defined) and the measurement model (which connects the latent constructs with their measurement indicators). Two types of techniques (methods) can be applied when modelling

structural equations: covariance-based techniques (CB-SEM), and partial least squares techniques based on variance (PLS-SEM).

Although both techniques have the same roots, Hair, Sarstedt, Ringle and Mena (2012) state that the covariance structural equation modelling (CB-SEM) approach is considered particularly useful when conducting theory testing. On the other hand, variance-based structural equation modelling (PLS-SEM) approach is considered a 'soft' modelling approach to be applied in predictive studies when proven theory does not exist, or when theoretical assumptions and methods of measurement are insufficiently developed. PLS-SEM technique maximizes the explained variance of the endogenous latent variables by estimating the partial relationships of the model in an iterative series of Ordinary Least Squares (OLS) regression. To summarize, PLS-SEM emphasizes prediction while relaxing data requirements and specifying relationships.

3. Results and discussion

Structural equation modelling using variance-based least squares technique (PLS-SEM) can be used to estimate parameters in hierarchical latent variable models. Testing of the reflective-reflective hierarchical latent model used in the study was conducted according to the recommendations of Hair et al. (2012) along with requirements regarding data and model characteristics.

In accordance with the criteria for evaluating the results of reflective models, and in accordance with the fact that the research used a reflective-reflective hierarchical latent model and within it the approach of repeating indicators, the constructs of all three hierarchical levels were tested by measuring: indicator reliability, internal consistency, convergent validity, and discriminant validity of latent constructs.

The composite reliability of the group of indicators which measure the construct is based on the Composite Reliability (CR) and Average Variance Extracted (AVE). Internal consistency was confirmed in all constructs measured by both indicators. If we take into account the Composite Reliability indicator, which represents the internal consistency of the test, i.e. the degree to which all test subjects covary with each other, with a limit of 0.7 as acceptable in Table 2, it is noticeable that for each construct the value of this indicator is in the range of 0.81 to 0.96.

The application of this indicator is more frequent for Confirmatory Factor Analysis (CFA),

